

A Prospective Study of Incidence, Causes and Management of Polyhydramnios at Tertiary Care Center

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Abstract:

Introduction: Polyhydramnios is a condition defined as a pathological increase in the volume of amniotic fluid during pregnancy. Common causes of polyhydramnios include gestational diabetes, congenital gastrointestinal anomalies like cleft palate, tracheoesophageal fistula, duodenal atresia, foetal infections, and others. Diagnosis is made via ultrasound, and the prognosis depends on the cause and severity. Mild forms often remain asymptomatic, while moderate to severe cases can result in complications such as maternal breathlessness, preterm labour, and premature rupture of membranes (PROM), cord prolapse, and postpartum haemorrhage (PPH).

Aim: This study was conducted to investigate the incidence, causes, and management of polyhydramnios.

Materials and Methods: We studied 106 clinically suspected cases of polyhydramnios beyond 28 weeks of gestation at M.P. Shah Medical College and G.G. Government Hospital, Jamnagar. All cases underwent ultrasonography for fetal surveillance and amniotic fluid index (AFI) calculation.

Results: The results of our study revealed that 49.06% of polyhydramnios cases were idiopathic, followed by 24.53% linked to gestational diabetes and 16.98% associated with fetal anomalies. Multiple pregnancies and Rh isoimmunization accounted for 5.66% and 3.77% of cases, respectively. Primigravida patients comprised 59.3% of the study population, indicating a higher prevalence of polyhydramnios in first-time mothers. Management of gestational diabetes was employed in 24.53% of cases, while 7.54% required reductive amniocentesis, and 0.94% were treated with indomethacin. Vaginal delivery was achieved in 79.2% of cases, while cesarean sections accounted for 20.8%, demonstrating that despite complications, the majority of patients could deliver vaginally with proper management.

Conclusion: In conclusion, most cases of polyhydramnios are idiopathic, with gestational diabetes and fetal anomalies being significant contributors to severe cases. Individualized management, timely screening, and monitoring are essential to ensure optimal outcomes, with delivery at tertiary care centers recommended for better maternal and fetal care.

Keywords: Idiopathic Polyhydramnios, Gestational Diabetes, Fetal Anomalies, Reductive Amniocentesis.

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Introduction

Polyhydramnios refers to the excessive accumulation of amniotic fluid during the antenatal period, often associated with high-risk pregnancies and poor outcomes. [1] The prevalence of polyhydramnios is reported to range between 0.2% and 1.6% of all pregnancies. [2] Amniotic fluid plays a critical role in the normal growth and development of the fetus. Any disruption in the balance of amniotic fluid production and reabsorption can significantly impact pregnancy outcomes. [3] The condition is more prevalent among high-risk groups, such as women with

maternal diabetes, placental diseases (e.g., chorioangioma), and various congenital anomalies. [4] Amniotic fluid is primarily produced by fetal urination and reabsorbed through fetal swallowing. In a healthy pregnancy, a balance between these two processes is maintained. However, disruptions in this equilibrium—such as compromised fetal swallowing or excessive urination—can lead to polyhydramnios. [5] Antepartum evaluation and fetal surveillance are essential in all cases of polyhydramnios to identify the underlying cause and guide clinical management. [6] In severe cases,

interventions like reductive amniocentesis and indomethacin may be required. Delivery in a tertiary care hospital is recommended to ensure optimal maternal and fetal outcomes. [7]

Materials and Methods

This prospective study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at M.P. Shah Medical College and G.G. Government Hospital, Jamnagar, Gujarat. The study spanned six months, from February 1, 2024, to July 31, 2024. During this period, the aim was to investigate the incidence, causes, and management of polyhydramnios. This tertiary care center provided access to a diverse population, making it an ideal setting for such a study.

The sampling method employed was universal sampling. All clinically suspected cases of polyhydramnios in the third trimester, defined as gestational age beyond 28 weeks, were included. Out of 18,000 patients who visited the Outpatient Department during the study period, 106 cases were identified and enrolled based on clinical suspicion. Inclusion criteria ensured that only patients presenting with signs of polyhydramnios during the third trimester were included for further assessment.

For every participant, detailed medical history was collected using standardized questionnaires, including demographic information, obstetric history, and possible risk factors for polyhydramnios. A thorough clinical examination was performed, with findings meticulously recorded. In addition to routine investigations, specific diagnostic tests were carried out based on individual patient presentations. Each patient underwent a detailed ultrasonographic evaluation to confirm the presence of polyhydramnios and to assess fetal well-being. The ultrasonographic examination was conducted with patients in a recumbent position using a 5.5 MHz linear probe

transducer. Amniotic fluid volume was assessed using the four-quadrant technique described by Phelan et al. [8] (1987), commonly referred to as the amniotic fluid index (AFI) method. In this method, the maternal abdomen was divided into four quadrants: the transverse line drawn through the umbilicus divided the abdomen into upper and lower halves, while the linea nigra divided it into right and left halves.

To measure the AFI, the transducer head was placed along the longitudinal axis of the maternal abdomen, and the maximum vertical pocket (MVP) of fluid in each quadrant was measured. The sum of the measurements from all four quadrants provided the AFI. The AFI levels were then used to classify the severity of polyhydramnios and guide subsequent management. Informed verbal consent was obtained from all study participants before their inclusion in the study, ensuring ethical compliance and patient autonomy.

This systematic and comprehensive approach ensured that each case was evaluated accurately, and the findings were used to tailor individualized management plans. Data collected from these patients provided valuable insights into the incidence, underlying causes, and effective management strategies for polyhydramnios at this tertiary care center.

Results

In our study, the prevalence of polyhydramnios was found to be 0.56% among all pregnancies beyond 28 weeks of gestation. This aligns with the reported prevalence range in the literature, which varies between 0.2% and 1.6% of all pregnancies. In our study, out of 106 cases of polyhydramnios, 76 cases had an AFI in the mild increased range (25-30 cm), 24 patients had an AFI of 30-35 cm (moderate polyhydramnios), and 6 patients had an AFI greater than 35 cm (severe polyhydramnios).

Table 1: Distribution of Study Subjects by Amniotic Fluid Volume by AFI

AFV	AFI (cm)	No. of Patients	Percentage
Mild increased	25-30 cm	76	71.69%
Moderately increased	30-35 cm	24	22.64%
Severely increased	>35 cm	6	5.66%

In our study, the distribution of subjects based on parity showed that 56 patients (59.3%) were primigravida, indicating that a majority of the women were experiencing their first pregnancy. On the other hand, 50 patients (40.7%) were multigravida, meaning they had experienced one or more previous pregnancies.

Figure 1: Parity distribution (%)

Table 2: Causes of Polyhydramnios

Causes	No. of Patients	Percentage
Idiopathic	52	49.06%
Maternal diabetes	26	24.53%
Fetal anomalies	18	16.98%
Multiple pregnancy	6	5.66%
Rh isoimmunization	4	3.77%

The analysis of causes of polyhydramnios in our study revealed that the largest proportion, 52 cases (49.06%), was idiopathic, meaning the cause remained unknown. Maternal diabetes accounted for 26 cases (24.53%), indicating a significant correlation between diabetes and polyhydramnios.

Fetal anomalies were identified as the cause in 18 cases (16.98%), while multiple pregnancies were responsible for 6 cases (5.66%). Rh isoimmunization contributed to polyhydramnios in 4 cases (3.77%).

Table 3: Various Pregnancy-Related Factors Associated with Polyhydramnios

Various Factors	No. of Patients	Percentage
Anemia	38	35.85%
Pregnancy-Induced Hypertension (PIH)	14	13.2%
Preeclampsia	5	4.72%
Multiple Gestation	6	5.66%
Rh Isoimmunization	4	3.77%
Diabetes	26	24.52%

In our study, several pregnancy-related factors were found to be associated with polyhydramnios. Anemia was the most common factor, present in 38 patients (35.85%), reflecting its high prevalence in developing countries. Pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) was identified in 14 patients (13.2%), while preeclampsia was observed in 5 patients (4.72%). Multiple gestations contributed to 6 cases (5.66%), with most involving twin pregnancies and one involving triplets. Rh isoimmunization was present in 4 cases (3.77%), indicating its role in contributing to abnormal amniotic fluid levels.

The treatment approach for polyhydramnios in our study varied depending on the severity and underlying causes. Idiopathic and mild cases of

polyhydramnios rarely required medical intervention. In cases of severe or symptomatic polyhydramnios, or when a fetal anomaly was detected, maternal-fetal medicine consultations were recommended to guide management. These cases were closely monitored with interval ultrasound scans to assess fetal growth and to determine the appropriate timing and mode of delivery.

For symptomatic relief, reductive amniocentesis was performed in cases where patients experienced significant respiratory discomfort due to restricted diaphragm movement or excessive amniotic fluid volume. The amount of amniotic fluid withdrawn depended on the severity of symptoms, with an average of 500-1000 mL removed during the

procedure. Although rare, potential complications associated with amniocentesis included preterm labor, placental abruption, and premature rupture of membranes (PROM). Indomethacin, a prostaglandin synthetase inhibitor, proved effective in reducing amniotic fluid volume and was also used as a tocolytic agent in cases of preterm labor. The recommended dose ranged from 0.2 to 3 mg/kg/day, depending on the clinical presentation. The timing of delivery was individualized, taking into consideration the severity of polyhydramnios,

the presence of congenital malformations, and complications such as preterm labor or PROM. Continuous fetal monitoring was essential during labor, as polyhydramnios increased the risk of delayed engagement of the fetal head, prolonging the first stage of labor. In cases where fetal head engagement was inadequate, the risk of umbilical cord prolapse was elevated, necessitating cesarean delivery to ensure the safety of both mother and baby.

Table 4: Treatment Given

Management	No. of Patients	Percentage
Management of gestational diabetes	26	24.53%
Reductive amniocentesis	8	7.54%
Indomethacin	1	0.94%

Figure 2: Mode of Delivery in Polyhydramnios

In our study, we observed that vaginal deliveries accounted for the majority of cases, comprising 79.2% of the total. This aligns with the general trend where vaginal delivery is preferred unless medical indications necessitate a cesarean section. Cesarean deliveries made up 20.8% of the cases, which falls within the typical range, as C-section rates can vary based on regional practices, healthcare settings, and individual patient factors.

Discussion

In our study, the distribution of amniotic fluid volume among participants showed that 71.69% had mild polyhydramnios (AFI 25-30 cm), 22.64% had moderate polyhydramnios (AFI 30-35 cm), and 5.66% presented with severe polyhydramnios (AFI >35 cm). This pattern aligns with the understanding that mild polyhydramnios is more common, often associated with idiopathic causes, and less likely to present significant complications.

Comparatively, Kaur et al. [9] found a higher incidence of mild polyhydramnios, with 77% of cases falling within the mild category, while moderate and severe cases were less frequent. Similarly, Aviram et al. [10] observed mild polyhydramnios to be a dominant finding in isolated cases, particularly in the absence of fetal or maternal complications. This prevalence is significant because mild polyhydramnios often requires less intervention and presents a lower risk profile compared to more severe cases. In contrast, Khatokar et al. [11] highlighted that severe polyhydramnios, although less frequent, was associated with greater risks such as preterm delivery and congenital anomalies, emphasizing the need for close monitoring in these cases. The consistency across studies underscores the need for routine AFI assessments to stratify risk and manage pregnancies appropriately. [11,12]

In our study, 59.3% of the participants were primigravida, while 40.7% were multigravida. This

distribution suggests a slightly higher representation of first-time mothers, which aligns with the clinical understanding that primigravida pregnancies may often require more frequent monitoring and intervention due to potential unfamiliarity with pregnancy management. Comparing with other studies, Aviram et al. [10] reported that isolated polyhydramnios was not predominantly associated with parity, with primigravida and multigravida distribution being relatively even, though primigravida cases showed a slightly higher frequency in requiring labor interventions such as induction or cesarean delivery. Similarly, in the study by Guin et al. [13], 13.3% of polyhydramnios cases were among nulliparous women, reflecting a need for clinical vigilance during the first pregnancy due to unfamiliar risks and a tendency toward more obstetric complications.

Furthermore, the study by Khatokar et al. [11] found that most cases of mild polyhydramnios were managed effectively regardless of parity, but severe cases were observed more frequently among multigravida women, suggesting a correlation between previous pregnancies and the severity of amniotic fluid disorders. Kaur et al. [9] also emphasized the importance of parity in determining clinical outcomes, noting that complications such as preterm labour were more common among multigravida participants due to cumulative maternal stress and previous obstetric histories.

In our study, the largest proportion of polyhydramnios cases (49.06%) was idiopathic, indicating no identifiable cause. Maternal diabetes was the second most common cause (24.53%), highlighting the well-known association between diabetes and increased amniotic fluid volume. Fetal anomalies contributed to 16.98% of the cases, emphasizing the link between structural abnormalities and excess fluid. Multiple pregnancies accounted for 5.66%, while Rh isoimmunization was identified in 3.77% of cases.

These findings align with other studies. Khatokar et al. [11] similarly observed that idiopathic polyhydramnios constituted a significant proportion (57%) of their cases, with diabetes being the leading maternal condition linked to polyhydramnios. Kaur et al. [9] further confirmed that idiopathic cases were prevalent in their cohort, accounting for about 50-60%, with maternal diabetes as a major contributing factor in the remaining cases. A study by Aviram et al. [10] also identified idiopathic causes as the most frequent, with diabetes-related cases showing a strong correlation with adverse perinatal outcomes, such as preterm labor and NICU admissions. The study by Guin et al. [13] emphasized fetal anomalies and multiple gestations as critical contributors to polyhydramnios, highlighting the need for fetal

anomaly screening in pregnancies with abnormal fluid levels. Moreover, Wassan et al. [14] noted that Rh isoimmunization, though less frequent, remains an important factor, particularly in regions with limited access to early intervention. In our study, the management of gestational diabetes was the most frequently employed intervention, accounting for 24.53% of cases. Reductive amniocentesis was performed in 7.54% of cases to relieve maternal discomfort and reduce risks of preterm labour. The use of indomethacin was limited to 0.94% of cases, reflecting the cautious approach toward pharmacological management. Vaginal deliveries were the predominant mode of delivery, representing 79.2% of cases, with cesarean sections accounting for 20.8%, in line with standard clinical practice where vaginal delivery is preferred unless complications necessitate surgical intervention. Comparing these findings with other studies, Aviram et al. [10] reported similar trends, where vaginal delivery was the preferred mode of delivery unless complicated by maternal or fetal factors. Their study highlighted that cesarean delivery rates increased with severe polyhydramnios, particularly when fetal anomalies or placental abnormalities were present. Khatokar et al. [11] also observed frequent use of reductive amniocentesis in their cohort, especially in cases with severe polyhydramnios, to prevent preterm labor and manage maternal discomfort.

A study by Kaur et al. [9] emphasized that the management of gestational diabetes played a crucial role in improving outcomes, as diabetes is a known contributor to polyhydramnios-related complications. Similarly, Guin et al. [13] highlighted that vaginal deliveries were feasible in most cases, with C-sections reserved for medical indications such as fetal distress or malpresentations, reinforcing the preference for non-surgical deliveries whenever possible. These consistent observations across studies highlight the importance of individualized management strategies, focusing on diabetes control, judicious use of reductive amniocentesis, and minimizing surgical interventions to ensure optimal maternal and fetal outcomes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, most cases of polyhydramnios are idiopathic, with gestational diabetes and fetal anomalies contributing to more severe presentations. Thorough evaluation, including screening for diabetes and detailed fetal anatomical surveys, is essential to guide management and prevent unnecessary interventions. While polyhydramnios is more common in primigravida patients, the mode of delivery remains comparable to pregnancies with normal AFI. Management should be individualized based on the severity and underlying causes, with mild cases often not

requiring treatment. For severe cases causing maternal discomfort, reductive amniocentesis can be considered. Close monitoring during labor is critical, and delivery at tertiary care facilities is recommended to ensure optimal maternal and fetal outcomes.

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